

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF PROCESSING OF DRY CHILLI IN NAGPUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

The present study "Economic analysis of processing of dry Chilli in Nagpur district" was conducted in Nagpur district. The data were collected with the help of specially prepare schedule by personal interview method. The total sample of 21 Chilli processing units were selected from study area. These processing units classified on per day installed processing capacity. The processing capacity of large sized units was 47 Qt./day, 25 Qt./day for medium sized units, and 10 Qt./day for small sized units. The actual processing capacity was found underutilized from installed processing capacity. The capital investment in small, medium and large chilli processing units was Rs. 1963929.27, Rs. 4542857.17 and Rs. 8685428.74 respectively. The overall capital investment in chilli processing units was Rs. 5064071.73. The per cent recovery from overall units by the processing of chilli was obtained as main product (chilli powder) 86.06 per cent, whereas moisture losses 4.88 per cent. Pedicel and stalk losses and loss in grinding and handling the chilli powder as 7.19 per cent, and 1.87 per cent processing losses respectively. The total cost of chilli processing per qtl. at overall level was Rs.19024.26. The per quintal gross returns at overall level obtained from chilli powder Rs. 24235.30. The overall net returns obtained from chilli was Rs. 5211.04. The overall cost: benefit ratio for chilli was 1: 1.27.

Keywords- Chilli, Capital Investment, Cost and Returns, Net returns, Benefit-Cost ratio.

Introduction

Processing of Agriculture products has assumed great importance now a days. Processing creates 'Form Utility' in the agriculture products which helps in fetching higher prices. The Processing and value addition of farm products has boosted agro - processing industry focusing in the rural area, which can generate large employment opportunities. Chilli is one of the most important commercial crops of India. It is grown almost throughout the country. There are more than 400 different varieties of chillies found all over the world. Different varieties are grown for vegetables, spices, condiments, sauces and pickles. Chilli occupies an important place in Indian diet. Chillies are rich in vitamins, especially in vitamin A and C. They are also packed with potassium, magnesium and iron. Chillies have long been used for pain relief as they are known to inhibit pain messengers, extracts of chilli peppers are used for alleviating the pain of arthritis, headaches, burns and neuralgia. It is also claimed that they have the power to boost immune system and lower cholesterol. They are also helpful in getting rid of parasites of gut. Chillies are the cheapest spices available in India and are eaten across all groups of people.

Chilli processing industry is a small-scale agro-industry in which majorly converts dry chilli to chilli powder in order to meet the local dietary needs and in which the meet the demands of local as well as

Table 1 Classification of chilli processing units on the basis of installed processing capacity

SR.NO.	Size Wise Group of unit	No. of Sample	Installed Capacity (Qt/day)	Actual processing Capacity (Qt/day)	Capacity Utilization (%)
1	Small	7	10	8	86.76
2	Medium	7	25	22	89.02
3	Large	7	47	43	91.46

As per the Table 1, it is observed that, the actual processing capacity utilized by small, medium and large sized chilli processing units were 86.76 per cent 89.02 per cent and 91.46 per cent respectively by comparing the installed processing capacity per day. Installed capacity was not fully utilized by chilli processing units because of their storage facility, unavailability of credit facilities, raw material and inadequate supply of skilled labour and a common factor of irregular power supply, applicable to all size of processing units.

Capital investment in chilli processing unit

It is observed from table 2 that, the capital investment in small, medium and large chilli processing units was Rs. 1963929.27, Rs. 4542857.17 and Rs. 8685428.74 respectively. The overall capital investment in chilli processing units was Rs.5064071.73.

some part of the neighbouring districts and state markets. These industries also provide gainful employment not only to the skilled but also unskilled labour.

Materials and Methods

For the present study, Nagpur district was purposively selected. The chilli processing units in Nagpur has varied installed processing capacity considered for selection of 21 processing units. Total 21 processing units was selected, 7 are small, 7 are medium and 7 are large sized processing units for the present study. The primary data were collected from selected chilli processing owner by personal interview method by the preparation of schedule and it was tested by asking the information from selected chilli processing owner. The collected information regarding cost and returns of chilli processing units asked by the chilli processing owner. The period of study was the year 2021-2022. The cost and returns of processing unit was worked out by using simple tabular analysis and benefit-cost ratio.

Results and Discussion

The empirical results of the study involving with a view to workout cost and returns.

Classification of chilli processing units on the basis of installed processing capacity

The selected chilli processing units were classified on the basis of their installed processing capacity and presented in Table No.1

At overall investment in machinery and accessories accounted 15.69 per cent, land investment was 28.59 per cent, building investment was 47.31 per cent, overall investment in power installation accounted 4.67 per cent, furniture investment was 3.74 per cent. Investment in land for small, medium and large sized processing units accounted 30.19 per cent, 28.21 per cent and 27.39 per cent respectively. Investment in building for small, medium and large sized processing units accounted 46.41 per cent, 47.48 per cent and 48.03 per cent respectively.

Investment in furniture for small, medium and large sized processing units accounted 3.38 per cent, 3.65 per cent and 4.18 per cent respectively. Investment in machinery and accessories for small, medium and large sized processing unit accounted 15.64 per cent,

16.05 per cent and 15.38 per cent respectively. Investment in power installation for small, medium and large sized processing unit accounted 4.38 per cent, 4.61 per cent and 5.03 per cent respectively.

The details of capital investment in chilli processing units are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Capital investment in chilli processing unit

(Rs./Unit)					
Sr. No.	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	Investment in Land	592857.14 (30.19)	1281428.57 (28.21)	2378571.47 (27.39)	1417619.06 (28.59)
2	Investment in Building	911428.63 (46.41)	2157142.86 (47.48)	4171428.61 (48.03)	2413333.37 (47.31)
3	Investment in Furniture	66429.21 (3.38)	165714.29 (3.65)	363142.89 (4.18)	198428.80 (3.74)
4	Investment in Machinery and accessories	307142.86 (15.64)	729285.71 (16.05)	1335714.31 (15.38)	790714.30 (15.69)
5	Power installation	86071.43 (4.38)	209285.74 (4.61)	436571.46 (5.03)	243976.21 (4.67)
6	Total	1963929.27 (100)	4542857.17 (100)	8685428.74 (100)	5064071.73 (100)

(Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to total investment)

Annual Recovery of dry chilli powder by processing unit

The details of recovery of dry powder by processing units are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Annual Recovery of dry chilli powder by processing unit

(Qtl./Unit)				
Particulars	Small Units	Medium Units	Large Units	Overall Units
Plant Operated (Days/Yr.)	280	274	289	281
Raw Material Processed (chilli)	2356.43	6034.14	12372.14	6920.90
Chilli Powder	1987.14 (84.33)	5227.86 (86.64)	10789.29 (87.21)	6001.43 (86.06)
Moisture Losses	132.14 (5.61)	282.14 (4.68)	540.86 (4.37)	318.38 (4.88)
Pedicel and Stalk Losses	174.29 (7.40)	429.27 (7.11)	872.14 (7.05)	491.90 (7.19)
Loss in Grinding and Handling the Chilli powder	62.86 (2.67)	94.88 (1.57)	169.86 (1.37)	109.19 (1.87)
Total Wastage	369.29 (15.67)	806.29 (13.36)	1582.86 (12.79)	919.48 (13.94)

(Figure in Parentheses indicate percentage to annual quantity chilli processed)

The details of recovery from processing of dry chilli by processing units are presented in Table no.3 for the financial year 2021-22. The table indicated that large processing units recovered 87.21 per cent from their total dry chilli processed, which is marginally higher compared to medium (86.64 per cent) and small (84.33 per cent) units. The loss in grinding and handling the chilli powder was more in small (2.67 per cent) units followed by medium (1.57 per cent) and large (1.37 per cent) units. Losses of chilli due to moisture in small (5.61 per cent), medium (4.68 per cent) and large (4.37 per cent) sized

processing unit and the losses of chilli by pedicel and stalk was marginally more in small (7.40 per cent) compared to medium (7.11 per cent) and large (7.05 per cent) dry chilli processing units.

The total wastage of chilli was considerably high in small (15.67 per cent), followed by medium (13.36 per cent) and large (12.79 per cent) dry chilli processing units.

Annual average fixed cost of chilli processing unit

The details of the annual fixed cost for small, medium and large chilli processing units are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Annual average fixed cost of chilli processing unit

(Rs./unit)					
Sr. No.	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	Depreciation on Building @5%	37394.41 (8.80)	100048.56 (9.25)	213772.68 (9.84)	117071.88 (9.30)
2	Opportunity cost of Land	24301.24 (5.72)	77318.88 (7.15)	141227.68 (6.50)	80949.27 (6.46)
3	Depreciation on Furniture @10%	3918.75 (0.92)	8432.54 (0.78)	18073.81 (0.83)	10141.70 (0.84)
4	Depreciation on Machineries @10%	19284.76 (4.54)	44142.86 (4.08)	85867.35 (3.95)	49764.99 (4.19)
5	Permanent Labour Wages	87157.14 (20.51)	240998.57 (22.29)	542532.86 (24.97)	290229.52 (22.59)
6	Taxes, licence fee and insurance premium	17257.14 (4.06)	65142.86 (6.02)	128857.14 (5.93)	70419.05 (5.34)

7	Interest on fixed capital @12%	235671.43 (55.45)	545142.86 (50.42)	1042251.43 (47.97)	607688.57 (51.28)
8	Total fixed cost	424984.88 (100)	1081227.12 (100)	2172582.94 (100)	1226264.98 (100)
9	Qty. of raw material Processed (chilli) (Qtl/Yr)	2356.43	6034.14	12372.14	6920.90
10	Fixed cost per Quintal	185.14	179.78	176.87	180.60

(Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to average fixed cost of chilli processing unit)

As revealed from table 4, the total annual average fixed cost for small, medium and large processing units were Rs. 424984.88, Rs. 1081227.12 and Rs. 2172582.94 respectively. It is observed from small group that, interest rate on fixed capital accounted a larger proportion i.e. 55.45 per cent (235671.43) of the total fixed cost followed by permanent labour charges with 20.51 per cent (87157.14), depreciation on building with 8.80 per cent (37394.41), opportunity cost of land with 5.72 per cent (24301.24) and lowest depreciation on furniture 0.92 per cent (3918.75).

In medium sized units, interest rate on fixed capitals was main item of fixed cost which accounted 50.42 per cent of the total fixed cost followed by permanent labour wages accounting 22.29 per cent, depreciation on building accounting 9.25 per cent, lowest cost was found in depreciation on furniture i.e. 0.78 per cent.

In large group units, interest rate on fixed capital accounted a larger proportion i.e. 47.97 per cent (1042251.43) of the total fixed cost followed by permanent labour charges with 24.97 per cent (542532.86), depreciation on building with 9.84 per cent

(213772.68), opportunity cost of land with 6.50 per cent (141227.68) and lowest depreciation on furniture 0.83 per cent.

Annual average variable cost of chilli processing unit

As evident from the Table 5, that annual average variable cost incurred for small, medium and large units was Rs. 43831612.95, Rs. 112623615.03, and Rs. 233440525.41 respectively. For overall annual average variable cost incurred in chilli processing was Rs. 129965251.13.

The total variable cost per quintal incurred for chilli was Rs. 18584.69, Rs.18715.29, and Rs. 18879.58 for small, medium, large sized units respectively. At overall was Rs. 18726.52.

The average variable cost for chilli products as states above of small, medium and large processing units increase with increase sized of units because the total of chilli processed was higher in large sized units as compare small and medium sized units as raw material required every year its cost changed according to level of production so it is consider as variable cost.

Table 5 Annual average variable cost of chilli processing unit

(Rs./Unit)					
Sr. No.	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	Raw material cost	39759692.23 (90.71)	102130033.07 (90.68)	211793502.19 (90.73)	117894409.16 (90.71)
2	Casual labour charges	14357.14 (0.03)	41142.86 (0.04)	77571.46 (0.03)	44357.15 (0.03)
3	Electricity charges	27285.71 (0.06)	79571.43 (0.07)	123714.31 (0.03)	76857.15 (0.06)
4	Repair and maintenance	12714.29 (0.03)	37557.14 (0.03)	59642.87 (0.03)	36638.10 (0.03)
5	Edible oil cost & lubricant	14142.91 (0.03)	43714.29 (0.04)	73071.45 (0.03)	43642.88 (0.03)
6	Water charges	6071.43 (0.01)	24571.44 (0.02)	43128.59 (0.02)	24590.49 (0.02)
7	Telephone & Telegraph charges	3614.29 (0.01)	9871.49 (0.01)	14142.89 (0.01)	9209.52 (0.01)
8	Other miscellaneous charges as gunny bag, labelling & stitching	9042.87 (0.02)	18642.86 (0.02)	33885.71 (0.01)	20523.81 (0.02)
9	Interest on Working Capital @10%	3984692.09 (9.09)	10238510.46 (9.09)	21221865.95 (9.09)	11815022.83 (9.09)
10	Total variable cost (Rs.)	43831612.95 (100)	112623615.03 (100)	233440525.41 (100)	129965251.13 (100)
11	Total raw material processed (Chilli) (Qtl.)	2356.43	6034.14	12372.14	6920.90
12	Total variable cost (Rs./Qtl.)	18584.69	18715.29	18879.58	18726.52

(Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to total variable cost of chilli processing unit)

It was observed from the table that, the expenditure incurred on the purchase of raw material was the main item of variable cost which constituted 90.71 per cent, 90.68 per cent and 90.73 per cent in small, medium and large sized units of processing respectively.

Table 6 Per quintal total cost and returns of processing of chilli

(Rs./Qtl.)					
Sr. No.	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
A	Chilli Powder (Per quintal of dry chilli) Costs				
	1) Fixed Cost	185.14 (0.98)	179.78 (0.95)	176.87 (0.92)	180.60 (0.95)

Per quintal total cost and returns of processing of chilli

The total cost of processing of chilli (including per quintal marketing cost) incurred by chilli processing owner is presented in table 6.

	2) Variable Cost	18584.69 (98.42)	18715.29 (98.44)	18879.58 (98.45)	18726.52 (98.43)
	3) Marketing Cost	114.15 (0.60)	117.57 (0.62)	119.70 (0.63)	117.14 (0.62)
	4) Total Cost	18883.98 (100)	19012.65 (100)	19176.15 (100)	19024.26 (100)
B	Chilli Powder (Per quintal of dry chilli) returns				
	1) Chilli Powder recovery (kg)	84.33	86.64	87.21	86.06
	2) Price (Rs/Kg)	281.43	279.71	283.76	281.63
	3) Gross returns	23725.57	24237.09	24743.25	24235.30
C	Net return (B-C)	4841.59	5224.44	5567.09	5211.04
D	Benefit-cost ratio (B-C ratio)	1.26	1.28	1.29	1.27

(Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to total cost and returns of chilli processing unit)

It is revealed from Table 6 that, the total cost processing of chilli is highest in large sized units was Rs. 19176.15 followed by medium and small sized unit accounted as Rs. 19012.65 and Rs. 18883.98 respectively. The overall units cost for processing of chilli was Rs. 19024.26. Among the total cost in overall units, the variable cost contribution (98.43 per cent), because of highest prices of raw material paid by entrepreneur in the market. In small, medium and large sized units the variable cost contributes 98.42 per cent, 98.44 per cent and 98.45 per cent respectively.

It is evident from Table No. 6 that, the per quintal gross returns from chilli powder in small, medium and large sized was Rs. 23725.57, Rs. 24237.09 and Rs. 24743.25 respectively. The overall gross returns for all sized unit was Rs. 24235.30.

The net returns obtained Rs. 4841.59, Rs. 5224.44 Rs. 5567.09 for small, medium and large sized chilli processing units respectively. The average net returns Rs. 5211.04 from chilli processing unit. The cost-benefit ratio for small, medium and large chilli processing units were 1:1.26, 1:1.28 and 1:1.29 respectively.

Conclusions

The large processing units recovered 87.21 per cent from their total dry chilli processed, which is marginally higher compared to medium (86.64 per cent) and small (84.33 per cent) units. The per quintal fixed cost was more in small chilli processing unit (Rs. 185.14) followed by medium (Rs. 179.78) and large processing unit (Rs. 176.87). The per quintal variable cost was more in large chilli processing unit (Rs. 18879.58) followed by medium (Rs. 18715.29) and small processing unit (Rs. 18584.69). The per quintal total cost of chilli processing was more in large processing unit (Rs. 19176.15) followed by medium (Rs. 19012.65) and small processing unit (Rs. 18883.98). The net returns per quintal for chilli processing were found to be higher in case of large sized processing units (Rs. 5567.09) as compared to medium (Rs. 5224.44) and small sized (Rs.4841.59) chilli processing units. Benefit cost ratio was also found to be higher in large sized chilli processing units.

References

1. **Khorne, W. K., S. J. Kakde and T. B Munde, 2019.** Economic analysis of processing of rice mill in Maharashtra. *International journal of chemical studies*, 7(4):1895-1899.
2. **Kondepudi, N., S. Sagar K. and Koripalli, 2015.** Investment pattern of paddy processing units: a case of east Godavari district in Andhra Pradesh. *International J. of Business Management & Research (IJBMR)*, 5(4):73-86.
3. **Vennila M. and C. Murthy, 2021.** Economics of production and processing of Pigeon pea in Karnataka. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, SP-10(10): 1056-1060.
4. **Wadkar, S.S., Gore, S.T., Mahindre Prakash, Malave, D.B. and M.B. Dalavi, 2016b.** Cashew processing in South-Konkan region- An economic analysis. *Maharashtra Journal of Agril. Economics Vol.19(1):* 227.
5. **Yadav, M. K. Subhita Kumawat, Subodh Agarwal and Sanjeev Kumar 2017.** Economics of gram processing in Rajasthan state. *Annals of Agri-Bio Research*, 23 (1): 37-39.